

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS

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Abstract

The article emphasizes that technology has developed exponentially in the last decade, it has affected our daily lifestyle and affected almost all industries, including international business. It is technology that makes international trade and business flourish, and without technology, international business developed slowly and was more labor intensive.

The information technology market is one of the newest and most rapidly emerging markets in the global economy. Its rapid development raises the question of a clear definition of its essence, features and commodity structure for researchers. International trade in information technologies, which arose only in the recent past, has reached a large scale in recent decades and has a significant impact on the pace of development of trade in other goods and services. With the increase in trade in information technologies and the growth of their importance for the national economies as a means of increasing the efficiency of production and the basis for creating new jobs, the attention of the world community to this commodity market is increasing. And as a consequence of this, there is a growing interest in more complete and comparable statistical data to determine the prospects and trends of market development.

The analysis of international trade in information technologies is associated with a number of difficulties, primarily related to the collection of statistical data. The main sources of this problem are the constant expansion of the forms of supply of information technology to the world market under the influence of scientific and technological progress; difference in the method of accounting for foreign trade operations in countries that are not members of the International Monetary Fund (IMF), which to a certain extent limits the completeness of information on this market).

Keywords: Economics, International business, Information technologies, e-commerce, globalization.

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Technology is no longer meant for individual countries or specific groups of people. These days, even the average person has access to some form of technology, which has contributed to the technological revolution and the revolution in international business.

The role of information technology in the development of international business is difficult to overestimate. They influence most areas of international business activity. Consideration should be given to the ways in which technology will affect international business and expectations for the future development of IT. Consider the following spheres of influence:

- telecommunications;
- social networks;
- logistics;
- production;
- market;
- electronic commerce;
- Internet banking [1].

In previous periods of development of international business, writing letters was the only way to communicate with international business partners. These letters could reach the addressee in days, weeks or months. At the moment, technology has shown high growth in this direction. Instant text and video messaging has become available via, for example, Skype or Zoom.

The concept of information and communication technologies appeared at the end of the 20th century. as a result of the convergence of communications and informatics, covering networks, technologies for processing and transmitting information and related services. These technologies should be understood as the activities of receiving, processing, accumulating, distributing and transmitting information through a combination of hardware and software, computing and telecommunications networks and information resources. In fact, ICT combines the communications industry and the information technology sector. The convergence of communications and informatics gave a new impetus to the development of all sectors of the national economy and social life in various directions and led to changes in the spheres of production and consumption of goods and services.

The high role of ICT in the economic development of society contributes to increasing the capabilities of national enterprises in ensuring effective social reproduction, in the growth of the country's participation in the international division of labor. The conducted research shows a close relationship between the level of the country's competitiveness in the world economy and the level of development of information and communication technologies in the country. ICT provides

the country with a more efficient use of available financial, production and labor resources, allows for the resolution of problems in a shorter time and at lower costs. Information and communication technologies are one of the main resources for development in this century. It includes the production of computer equipment, digital communications, the production of software and information services. The contribution of this sector to GDP growth in industrialized countries is about 30%, and the share of employment in the information and communication technology sector in developed countries exceeds this article [2].

In the context of the dynamic development of the economy and the development of market structures in Azerbaijan, the innovative development of all industries and sectors of economic activity is becoming increasingly important. In this process, a special place is given to the development of ICT as a branch of industrial and social infrastructure, the innovation policy in which directly and indirectly affects the management system and the activities of all sectors of the national economy. The widespread use of ICT in other industries brings them to a qualitatively new level of development through the introduction of information technologies, allows them to increase labor productivity and, in turn, accelerate growth rates. A growing ICT industry is a necessary condition for economic recovery.

In addition, it should be noted that in the country's economy, information and communication technologies represent a national commodity resource that was previously used to develop exports. The cadres of specialists currently available in the country testify to the possibility of using them to expand national exports.

Telecommunication technology is what makes international business possible. They are needed to send invoices, work with clients, communicate with suppliers and keep in touch with employees who may live in other parts of the world.

Internet technologies and, in particular, web conferencing, make it possible to hire employees living in other countries. As a result, companies have more opportunities to find key people and save money because they do not need to build a physical office for these employees [3].

Directly hired international employees can often do their jobs from home as long as they have an internet connection. Companies also have the opportunity to hire remote employees through outsourcing centers that provide a workplace and the necessary equipment.

By hiring remote workers around the world, companies can also benefit if they have employees in the same country where key suppliers, vendors and customers are located. Employees around the world not only add variety to the company's activities, but also provide the company with key personnel who can speak the native language of a given country and understand the customs of this country. Such employees, if necessary, can help in holding regional meetings and optimizing business processes in a foreign country.

Speaking of social media, we can say that social media is a branch of telecommunications technology, but it deserves special attention, since social media has given international business a platform through which

it can show rapid growth in a short time. Social media tracks global trends in fashion, decor, art, furniture and a variety of other products, which gives international businesses a wealth of information that can be used to minimize costs and maximize profits [4].

Whether it's Instagram, Facebook, Linked In or others, having a social media account allows international companies to connect with their target audience around the world and advertise their products to them. Previously, people found out about the enterprises of other countries with a delay, which, at the moment, with the help of social networks, has become faster and easier.

The impact of information technology on logistics is also high. Over the past 80 years or so, there have been several significant advances in this area. Customers no longer want to wait long for the goods they order, as commercial jets have made the transportation of goods to different parts of the globe affordable and timely. These days, customers are looking for instant satisfaction for their shopping needs, so great care is taken to ensure that orders are delivered as quickly as possible.

The development of air travel and airports around the world has also made travel more affordable for overseas business partners and created a huge boom in the travel industry, creating opportunities for many international businesses.

The use of modern supply chain management software has simplified the management of global procurement, instead of purchasing goods and raw materials within the country of deployment. International business uses this to reduce costs, increase resource efficiency, and also to have greater diversity in raw materials, since the country's domestic market may not fully cover the needs of production.

Information technology has not bypassed the production. An international business that sells goods has already experienced the latest innovations in this field. Technology has played an important role in all manufacturing and related processes such as production planning, financial planning and marketing. Thanks to technology, companies can have manufacturing plants in several different countries, and there is a choice in determining the location of their production, based on where it is easier to get materials and where skilled labor is more affordable [5].

The globalization of the market began to take shape when the transportation and sale of goods in different countries became more accessible and expedient. The Internet is seen as a low-cost network of market globalization in electronic form. Thanks to social media, television and the low cost of transporting goods around the world, there has been a kind of convergence of consumer preferences and tastes. For example, there was a time when only Americans wore jeans, but now people all over the world are interested in buying and wearing jeans, and this is how the globalization of the market works. The same thing happens with brands like McDonald's, Pizza Hut and so on. A global culture is being created in which different countries begin to have similar wish lists and requirements.

E-commerce platforms are platforms or websites that specialize in selling goods over the Internet, usually to an international audience. Over the years, one can observe numerous advances in e-commerce technology. The result has been achieved where almost anyone can create their own e-commerce site without too much trouble, thanks to all the templates and apps available. This makes it possible for both ordinary people and multi-million dollar corporations to sell their products via the Internet. E-commerce platforms are usually fully integrated with shipping, payment, and customer service systems.

In a broad sense, e-commerce platforms can be a combination of two elements:

1) combining new technologies with elements of traditional stores and direct mail models;

2) the use of new technologies to replace elements of store or direct mail retail.

In this case, the following business models apply.

B2C, business-to-consumer communication, is a type of e-business communication in which the sale is made to members of the public. This allows consumers to go online and buy a product, and allows businesses of any size to find their target audience around the world. This type includes Internet commerce, interactive television, electronic mail and telephone sales.

The next type is B2B, the business-to-business model - an electronic transaction between a manufacturer and its intermediaries, belongs to the field of B2B e-commerce. It is usually assumed that there is some form of contractual relationship between the supplier and the company, and is mainly used for corporate procurement. Trade information and communication between the parties is exchanged electronically using agreed protocols implemented through special commercial solutions designed to facilitate this exchange. It includes bidding on the Internet, electronic document management systems.

Next, consider the C2B model, consumer-to-business communication is another type of e-commerce that allows a potential organization, manufacturer, and even service center to visit their website and offer to buy existing products at the asking price. When an organization accepts their offer, the consumer is obligated to sell the product to that organization.

B2G, business-to-government communication is a new type of communication that involves an electronic transaction between government and business organizations. It includes government tenders, trade procedures, for example, with clients, and so on.

C2C, e-commerce without the participation of business and intermediaries, only between consumers. This is the last type of communication in e-commerce. After receiving an advertisement for the sale of a certain product from any consumer through a consumer exchange site, it is possible to purchase this product at a negotiated price.

Also, information technology has played a significant role in the development of Internet banking, over the past few years one can observe a high level of growth. Paying online, regardless of location, is easier than ever before for customers around the world. You can use a credit card, payment solutions like Raural,

and digital currencies like Wisot in some cases. In addition, exchange rates and payment fees are lower, making international shopping easier and more affordable for the average consumer.

Another important role of information technology in international business is that it has made it easier for companies around the world to learn from each other and make more informed international business decisions. Tech companies in Asia can go online and learn about the products, financial position, and marketing capabilities of their US competitors to better assess their strengths and weaknesses. At the same time, US companies can research overseas markets for their products and assess where business expansion would make financial sense.

Ultimately, online research opportunities can help companies gain a competitive advantage over foreign competitors. It can also encourage innovation when ideas arise to improve an existing product or service to meet the needs of a particular market.

You also need to touch on marketing. The importance of information technology and international marketing comes from how the Internet allows companies to interact with customers around the world. Instead of relying on costly advertising in print, TV and radio, companies can pay for cheaper online advertising through global search engines, register in global business directories and advertise on social media. They can even hire remote marketers in the target region [6].

Companies can also use tools such as customer relationship management (CRM) software to tailor their marketing campaigns to each market's culture and customer preferences. CRM systems help track marketing analytics to understand customer experiences with products and services, and to optimize communications with customers around the world through automated emails and response tracking systems.

Thus, information technology has increased the efficiency of international companies in various business sectors. Whether a company needs to find the best supply chains, study a foreign competitor, provide digital services, find remote employees, or mass-produce products overseas, they can do it quickly through web searches or corporate programs.

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DETERMINATION OF THE PROPERTIES AND COMPOSITION OF OIL, GAS AND CONDENSATE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF WELLS BY DUAL COMPLETION

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of the properties and compositions of oil, gas and condensate to determine their heterogeneity during their jointly separate operation by the method of dual completion (DC). In order to successfully implement the DC method simultaneously in gas reservoirs in one and in another second elevator of oil reservoirs in one well, comparative laboratory analyses and field studies on the properties and compositions of oil, gas and condensate were carried out, which determine a significant role in the development of wells dual completion.

Keywords: methane, nitrogen, carbon dioxide, asphalt, sulfur, paraffin, free gases.

Simultaneous development of several formations by one object is possible only with the same physical and chemical properties of oils in the combined formations, if the inflow of oil and gas is sufficient from each formation at an acceptable bottom-hole pressure in the well, with close values of reservoir pressure in the combined formations, excluding oil flows between the layers, and close values of reservoir waterlogging. If the above conditions are not met, then multidimensional deposits are developed by the DC method with one well [1].

At the Altyguyi deposit in the NK₉ horizon, free gases contain 97.90% methane, up to 1.19% of its homologues, up to 0.70% nitrogen and 0.21% carbon dioxide.

In the NK_{7g} horizon, free gases contain 97.20% methane, up to 1.54% of its homologues, 0.67% nitrogen and 40.17% carbon dioxide.

In the NK₈ horizon, free gases contain 97.20% methane, up to 2.08% of its homologues, 0.55% nitrogen and 0.17% carbon dioxide. The oil of the NK₉ horizon has a density of 0.9065 g / cm³, solidifies at a temperature of +33 °C, the viscosity at a temperature of 50 °C is 51.69 Pz, and at a temperature of 20 °C does not flow.

Up to a temperature of 300 °C, it boils by 19%. The composition contains 4.7% asphaltene, 16.7% resins, 21.4% paraffin and 0.41% sulfur.

According to the group hydrocarbon composition, they belong to the methane-naphthenic geochemical type (H: M 0.99), contain 13% aromatic, 43.3% naphthenic and 43.7% methane hydrocarbons.

The density of condensates of the NK_{7g} horizon is 0.7 0.53 g / cm³, solidify -3 °C, viscosity at a temperature of 20 °C 1.79 Pz. Up to a temperature of 300 °C, boil up to 77%.

According to the group hydrocarbon composition, they belong to the methane-naphthenic geochemical type. (H: M 0.83), contain 9.0% aromatic, 41.7% naphthenic and 49.3% methane hydrocarbons (Table 1.2).

The density of condensates of the NK₉ horizon is 0.7971 g/cm³, they solidify at a temperature equal to +3 °C, the viscosity at a temperature of 20 °C is 1.8 s Pz. Up to a temperature of 300 °C, up to 76% is boiled off. The composition contains 1.4 resin, 3.5% paraffin and asphaltene is absent. By group composition, they belong to the methane-naphthenic geochemical type (H:0.84) and contain 9.9% aromatic, 41.2% naphthenic and 48.9% methane hydrocarbons.

Table 1

Properties and composition of the gas
(average value over the horizons)

Horizon	Interval Perforations, (m)	Density		Quantity, % volume			
		g/l	by air	CO ₂	Nitrogen	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₆
Soluble gases							
NK-9	3670-3680	0,742	0,574	0,21	0,70	97,90	1,60
Free gases							
NK -7d	3512-3624	0,738	0,571	0,22	0,67	97,57	0,94
NK -8	3616-3625	0,737	0,570	0,17	0,55	97,20	1,14